

Analysis of Interactive Marketing as an Intervening on the Effect of Internal Marketing and Customer Orientation on Marketing Performance

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Abstract:- A strategic plan has been designed by an Indonesian social security agent called "Perisai Agent" to expand participation and improve the quality of service of BPJS Ketenagakerjaan. The implemented service marketing strategy consists of three elements: internal marketing, external marketing and interactive marketing, known as service triangle marketing. The purpose of this study is to analyze the marketing strategy of the service triangle marketing model, specifically by investigating the effect of internal marketing and customer orientation on the marketing performance mediated by interactive marketing of Perisai Agents of BPJS Ketenagakerjaan in West Nusa Tenggara. This is a quantitative research based on associative causality. The research sample was obtained using probability sampling data collection techniques and the Slovin formula, resulting in a total of 100 respondents selected through proportionate random sampling via the distribution of questionnaires. The data analysis was conducted using the Structural Equation Model (SEM) approach based on Partial Least Square (PLS) with SMART PLS software. The analysis results show that internal marketing has no significant effect on marketing performance; customer orientation and interactive marketing have a significant effect on marketing performance; internal marketing and customer orientation have a significant effect on interactive marketing. The indirect test demonstrates that interactive marketing, as an intervening variable, is able to mediate the effect of internal marketing and customer orientation on marketing performance.

Keywords:- Perisai Agent, Internal Marketing, Customer Orientation, Interactive Marketing, Marketing Performance.

I. INTRODUCTION

Social security protection is an important aspect of people's lives in the current era of globalisation and modernisation with economic complexity and social dynamism. Social protection covers health, education and employment. It is an important foundation for a country's social welfare. In Indonesia, the Employment Social Security Agency (BPJS Ketenagakerjaan) is one of the institutions that plays a crucial role in providing social protection, especially in the field of employment. BPJS Ketenagakerjaan's mission is to provide social security to all workers in Indonesia and to

cover social risks such as occupational accidents, occupational diseases and death. In an effort to achieve its mission, BPJS Ketenagakerjaan cannot be separated from the role of effective and efficient marketing. Good marketing can help BPJS Ketenagakerjaan realise the benefits of increasing participation, providing clear information to participants, and ensuring sufficient funds to meet claims payment needs.

As a social security service institution in Indonesia, marketing presents several challenges for us. Factors such as changes in the economic landscape, government policies, modifications in consumer behavior patterns, and socio-cultural conditions of the community are prominent determinants affecting our marketing performance. Therefore, a comprehensive comprehension and objective assessment of marketing effectiveness at BPJS Ketenagakerjaan is crucial in providing profound insights into how this institution can enhance marketing strategies, maximize advantages, and uphold participants' and community's rights to social protection.

BPJS Ketenagakerjaan currently offers five social security protection programs for employees in Indonesia. These programs include Employment Injury Security (JKK), Death Security (JKM), Old Age Security (JHT), Pension Guarantee (JP), and Unemployment Benefit (JKP). They are available for workers in the Wage Receptant Workers (PU), Non-Waged Workers (BPU), Construction Services Workers (Jakon), and Migrant Workers (PMI) sectors. BPJS Ketenagakerjaan evaluates its marketing performance by measuring the level of membership coverage. This measurement is based on the comparison between the number of working people who actively participate in BPJS Ketenagakerjaan during a certain period of time.

Over the past five years, the National Employment Survey conducted by the Central Bureau of Statistics (Sakernas BPS) of West Nusa Tenggara Province has shown an annual increase in the number of workers. However, this growth has not been matched by an increase in the number of active participants who meet the BPJS Ketenagakerjaan target, as of 2021. As of 2022, the number of active participants reached 519,666 people, which equates to 19.12% membership coverage. However, this percentage falls short when considering participation coverage and is still relatively low compared to the national membership coverage of BPJS

Ketenagakerjaan, which was 44.96% in the same year. Furthermore, it is lower than the 2018 coverage rate of 22.87%. According to Susanto (2016), inadequate employment social security can lead to insufficient basic living needs in the event of work accidents or death, resulting in loss or reduction of income. This requires continual innovation and making new breakthroughs to increase membership.

In addition to adapting technology for developing a strategic plan to expand membership and improve service quality, BPJS Ketenagakerjaan has achieved a breakthrough by creating the Indonesian Social Security Agent (Perisai). This innovative approach is organized through an agency system and is referred to as the "Perisai Agent". Perisai Agent is a new BPJS Ketenagakerjaan strategy that establishes a field market force to enhance the coverage of employment protection and social security by expanding into the informal worker sector and non-waged workers. The aim is to provide better protection and security to a broader range of workers by utilizing this strategy.

As BPJS Ketenagakerjaan employees, Perisai Agents are marketers who directly interact with the public or customers. A strategy is necessary to provide excellent customer service outcomes. According to Hasan (2023), Service Triangle Marketing, consisting of internal marketing, external marketing, and interactive marketing, is a crucial service marketing strategy for service companies. Companies, employees, and customers are all integral components of this strategy. The success of BPJS Ketenagakerjaan marketing is determined by the effectiveness of Perisai Agent in implementing marketing activities. Therefore, companies should focus on internal aspects, specifically employees, through implementing internal marketing strategies. Qaisar and Muhamad (2021) demonstrate that companies that adopt internal marketing initiatives can enhance their employees' comprehension of their responsibilities and contributions to the company's performance, which includes achieving marketing objectives. This has been established in the research conducted by Aji (2016) and Sigit & Muafi (2022), which asserts that internal marketing has a significant and positive effect on marketing performance.

Customer orientation, as defined by Atuahene-Gima and Ko (2001), denotes a company's strategic focus on promoting and supporting the collection, dissemination, and response to market intelligence that serves customer needs. It is a crucial factor in generating marketing performance (Rachmat, 2018). This position is also supported by Suarniki (2015), who states that one of the factors that can affect marketing performance is customer orientation. One strategy employed by BPJS Ketenagakerjaan to achieve effective marketing performance is enhancing customer-oriented strategies that identify customers' preferences and needs. In BPJS Ketenagakerjaan's customer orientation strategy, Perisai Agents play a vital role in obtaining information about participants' needs and preferences, as they directly interact with them. According to Valentine and Devie (2015), effective customer orientation enhances company performance. Additionally, using customer orientation enables the marketing information system to

monitor consumers, ensuring organizational success. This research demonstrates that customer orientation positively and significantly impacts marketing performance (Haryanto et al., 2017). This finding is also supported by Purwasari and Budi (2014) and Fatolah and Nugroho (2017), who assert that customer orientation can improve marketing performance. However, Jayaningrum and Sanawiri (2018) presented differing results which demonstrate that customer orientation does not have a significant impact on marketing performance.

Marketing performance measures the achievement an organization has obtained through its marketing activities, according to Suyatno et al. (2023). Effective employee communication and customer interaction are important factors in achieving the desired marketing performance. Interactive marketing involves two-way communication between employees and customers, where customers share their views, choices, and preferences about products so that marketers can make them better (Hsieh, 2017). Perisai Agents providing BPJS Ketenagakerjaan services can conduct interactive marketing directly in the field or through online channels. Kotler and Keller (2009) defined interactive marketing as online activities and programs aimed at directly or indirectly engaging customers, increasing awareness, improving image, or generating sales of products and services. Perisai Agents implementation of interactive marketing is believed to have the potential to enhance marketing performance. This claim is confirmed by the research results of Kaunda, Thuo & Kwendo (2023); Stone & Laughlin (2016) and Hsieh (2017), which showed that interactive marketing has a positive and significant effect on marketing performance.

The implementation of internal marketing at Perisai Agents is expected to improve interactive marketing. Huang & Lee's (2012) research results support this, stating that internal marketing at the group level has a positive and significant effect on interactive marketing at the individual level. Furthermore, Hsieh (2017) explains that the interaction effect of internal marketing and interactive marketing has a significant effect. Similarly, when each Perisai Agent is able to focus on the participants (customer orientation), it is expected to enhance interactive marketing. No studies have discovered a connection between customer orientation and interactive marketing. However, according to Conduita et al (2014), it is crucial to test interactive marketing empirically in both internal and external customer orientation research. Additionally, they acknowledged that including the perspective of interactive marketing would provide a more comprehensive study, which they hope to conduct in future studies. Improving Perisai Agents' internal marketing and customer orientation is expected to improve interactive marketing so that it can build better interactive content to be applied to customers, which in turn is expected to improve BPJS Ketenagakerjaan's marketing performance.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. *Service Triangel Marketing*

In 1978, Thomas introduced the structure of the service marketing triangle model, which is composed of external marketing, internal marketing, and interactive marketing. According to Sunarto (2016), the service marketing triangle is one of several elements that define the relationship between companies and customers. The three elements include the management side of the company, employees or workers, and customers. Kotler (1997) and Kumar et al., (2020) emphasizes the importance of organizations engaging in marketing through the development of meaningful relationships with both customers and employees. Hsieh's (2017) research indicates that internal, interactive, and external marketing have significant impact on customer satisfaction.

B. *Marketing Performance*

Marketing performance is the result of the implementation of marketing activities carried out by a company, marketing performance or marketing performance is a concept to measure the marketing success of a company, every company has an interest in knowing its performance as a reflection of the success of its business in market competition (Zebua, et al., 2023). Marketing performance refers to the measurement of the success of marketing programs, including the outcomes of implemented marketing activities. It aims to focus on the alignment of marketing activities, strategies, and business objectives to improve financial results. (Ambler, et al., 2004). Marketing performance is evaluated by measuring the effectiveness of the marketing strategy implemented by the company, which can be done by analyzing sales growth, customer growth, and profitability (Ferdinand, 2000). Marketing performance measurement is part of performance measurement (business), which is a field of science that aims to support the implementation of business strategy by creating insights about company performance (Utami et al., 2022).

C. *Internal Marketing*

Internal marketing is a strategy utilized by companies to improve their products and services and enhance their performance. It is vital for companies to value internal operational activities, especially concerning human resources (Jumadi, 2015). Kotler & Keller (2012) define internal marketing as a component of holistic marketing, which encompasses the recruitment, training, and motivation of employees to provide customers with excellent service. According to Barnes and Morris (2000), the objective of internal marketing activities is to establish an internal environment that promotes customer awareness and sales attention. Internal marketing is deemed significant as it has a substantial impact on a business's prosperity, enhances employee satisfaction, and creates organizational commitment. Qaisar and Muhamad (2021) suggest that organizations that adopt internal marketing strategies can enhance their employees' perception of their role and contribution to the organization's or company's performance.

D. *Customer Orientation*

Narver and Slater (1990) describe customer orientation as a component of market orientation of a company's survival strategy. By applying customer orientation, the marketing information system will be able to track consumers so that organizational performance (sales growth, market share increase, etc.) can be ensured (Valentine and Devie, 2015). Atuahene-Gima and Ko (2001) assert that customer orientation reflects a company's strategic focus on the market and is defined as promoting and supporting the collection, dissemination, and response to market intelligence to respond to customer needs. In addition, Saura et al (2005) define customer orientation as a type of organizational orientation in which consumer needs become the basis for an organization to plan and design its strategy.

E. *Interactive Marketing*

Kotler and Keller (2012: 478) define interactive marketing as online activities and programs aimed at influencing all marketing and promotional efforts. Furthermore, interactive marketing encompasses communication that extends from employees to customers substantiate and fulfill the promises that companies make to customers through external marketing communication (Katti & Mutmainah, 2020). In this interactive marketing context, employees are required to deliver messages and provide the best service to customers.

F. *The Relation between Internal Marketing and Marketing Performance*

Internal marketing is an attempt to attract, develop, motivate, and retain qualified employees in the organization's efforts to satisfy customer needs (Cahill, 1996). Schroeder (2000) purports that the principal element to attain service profitability lies in prioritizing customers and employees as the most vital aspect of a company. However, management may at times solely concentrate on a predetermined set of objectives or service positioning, overlooking the concerns of frontline employees, who ultimately implement those services. Managers should prioritize front-line employees who provide services, supporting technology, training, and customer satisfaction to increase their productivity. According to Cahill (1996) and Foreman (1999), the exchange relationship between companies and employees is the initial step in achieving corporate goals in the external market. This has been supported by Aji's (2016) and Sigit & Muafi's (2022) research, which demonstrates that internal marketing efforts have a substantial positive impact on marketing performance.

H1: *Internal marketing has a positive and significant effect on the marketing performance of Perisai Agents*

G. *The Relation between Customer Orientation and Marketing Performance*

Market orientation is crucial for enhancing company performance as it involves understanding consumers, knowing competitors' strategies, and coordinating between functions within the company. Customer orientation is a vital element of market orientation. Therefore, companies must prioritize their focus on customer satisfaction and tailor their operations accordingly. Customer orientation is an intangible resource forming the organizational culture of a company that aims to

create additional value for customers and can enhance business performance, including marketing (Narver and Salter, 1990). Customer orientation encompasses all activities that enhance a company's comprehension of its target customers' needs and preferences, along with its ability to design products and services that satisfy these needs and preferences. Effective customer orientation can improve a company's performance (Valentine and Devie, 2015). After using orientation, the marketing information system will be able to track consumers so that organizational performance (sales growth, market share increase, etc.) can be guaranteed. This research is also confirmed by Feng et al. (2019); Frambach et al. (2016); Ziggers & Henseler, (2016); Lisa (2015) and Asikhia (2010), who found that customer orientation has a significant impact on firm performance. Other studies have demonstrated the significance of customer orientation in enabling companies to gain a deeper understanding of customer demand, leading to enhanced sales growth (Feng et al., 2012 and Valenzuela et al., 2010). Additionally, it helps to attain a competitive advantage and achieve business success (Ziggers & Henseler, 2016).

H2: *Customer orientation has a positive and significant effect on the marketing performance of Perisai Agents.*

H. The Relation between Internal Marketing and Interactive Marketing

According to Gronroos (1990), internal marketing describes the efforts made by companies to train and motivate employees so that they are interested in making maximum contributions in marketing services to consumers. Meanwhile, interactive marketing describes the expertise of employees in serving customers. Thus, it can be concluded that internal marketing and interactive marketing to employees are interrelated and mutually supportive. Interactive marketing to employees can be formed through internal marketing organized by the company. Since employees are expected to be loyal, highly motivated, and empowered to provide maximum service to consumers, the development of expertise and motivation can be done through the company's internal marketing programs such as coffee morning, in-house training, benchmarking, and other activities conducted regularly. Therefore, it can be said that internal marketing can influence the interactive marketing of a company, which is supported by Hsieh's research (2017), which states that internal marketing supports interactive marketing.

H3: *Internal marketing has a positive and significant effect on the interactive marketing of Perisai Agent*

I. The Relation between Customer Orientation and Interactive Marketing

Customer orientation is used as a business survival strategy. Atuahene-Gima & Ko (2001) state that customer orientation is defined as a firm's orientation toward promoting and supporting the collection, dissemination, and response to market information to serve customer needs. Customer orientation is concerned with identifying and meeting customers to gain sufficient knowledge to generate more value for customers. Meanwhile, inter-functional coordination describes cross-functional cooperation within the organization. Customer orientation can help BPJS Ketenagakerjaan Perisai Agents understand customer needs

and wants so that they can design interactive Perisai Agent marketing strategies that are more effective and relevant. By understanding customers well, companies can develop interactive content that is more interesting and useful to customers, which can increase customer loyalty and satisfaction and have an impact on marketing performance. Then, it can be concluded that customer orientation is related to interactive marketing in companies because companies will have better performance when they are market oriented (Gronroos, 2006).

H4: *Customer orientation has a positive and significant effect on the interactive marketing of Perisai Agent.*

J. The Relation between Interactive Marketing and Marketing Performance

Interactive marketing is a promotion by creating two-way communication between customers and companies and by using online marketing to meet the needs and wants of consumers (Kotler and Keller, 2009). According to Wang (2021), interactive marketing is the latest and current marketing trend due to the dynamic and technologically advanced character of today's customers. Therefore, a deeper understanding of consumer behavior and preferred interaction methods is required to provide individualized, valuable, and engaging experiences. By studying consumer behavior, it can increase awareness, improve image and create product or service sales, increase purchases and increase consumer loyalty, which is an achievement in an organization or company described as a result of marketing performance. Thus, it can be said that increasing interactive marketing can improve the company's marketing performance, which is supported by the research of Stone & Laughlin (2016); Hsieh (2017) and Kaunda, Thuo & Kwendo (2023).

H5: *Interactive marketing has a positive and significant effect on the marketing performance of Perisai Agent*

III. RESEARCH METHOD

This study uses a quantitative approach. Quantitative research is a type of research that collects numerical data and uses statistical analysis to explain phenomena. (Creswell, 2014). The type of research used is causal associative, which is research that examines the relationship between one or two other variables (Sugiyono, 2014). The sample size was obtained using the Slovin formula and the sample was collected using the proportional random sampling technique, which is 100 respondents. The data were collected using a questionnaire with a semantic differential scale of 1-10, from strongly disagree to strongly agree. Then, the research data were analyzed by using Partial Least Square-Structural Equation Model (PLS-SEM) with smart PLS software.

IV. RESULTS

To evaluate the PLS structural model for hypothesis testing, we utilize the percentile-based bootstrapping process. We employ the t-test as a statistical test in this method. The results show that the t-values for the two-way (two-tailed) test have significance at 1.96 (at a 5% level of significance). According to the t-test criteria, if the t-statistic value is higher than the t-table or the significance value is less than 0.05, then

the hypothesis can be accepted. Bootstrapping calculations are obtained through the path coefficient, which measures the strength of the effect of the independent variable on the dependent variable. Additionally, this paper identifies the effect of an independent variable on the dependent variable through the mediating variable in an analysis.

The t-statistics and probability values obtained from bootstrapping during hypothesis testing are presented in Figure 1. Table 1 contains the results of the hypothesis testing and Table 2 the results of the indirect effect test.

Fig 1. Path Coefficient

Table 1. Hypothesis Test Results

Relations	Coefficients	T Statistic	P Value	Effect
X1 -> Y	-0.057	0.647	0.259	Negative Not Significant
X2 -> Y	0.288	3.074	0.001	Positive Significant
X1 -> Z	0.350	3.529	0.000	Positive Significant
X2 -> Z	0.350	2.962	0.002	Positive Significant
Z -> Y	0.676	8.880	0.000	Positive Significant

Table 2. Indirect Correlation Effect Test Result

Relations	Coefficients	T Statistic	P Value	Effect
X1 -> Z -> Y	0.237	3.181	0.001	Positif, Signifikan
X2 -> Z -> Y	0.236	2.828	0.002	Positif, Signifikan

V. DISCUSSION

A. The Effect of Internal Marketing on Marketing Performance

The study found that internal marketing had a negative and insignificant effect on marketing performance, which means that better implementation of internal marketing did not have a better effect on the marketing performance of BPJS Ketenagakerjaan Perisai Agents. The findings of this research that measure the direct effect of the variable under study offer valuable insights by adding new facts. The present study's results differ from those reported by Aji (2016) and Sigit & Muafi (2022), indicating that internal marketing activities have a significant positive effect on marketing performance. However, the use of different indicators or variable dimensions in research can influence the research outcomes. Internal marketing is evaluated based on three dimensions established by Foreman and Arthur (1995) and Rafiq & Ahmed (2000): service training programmes, performance incentives, and a vision of service excellence. Marketing

performance is measured using three indicators adjusted to the Key Performance Indicator (KPI) of BPJS Ketenagakerjaan: sales growth through the addition of new participants, customer growth through growth of active participants, and increase in contribution receipts. These marketing performance indicators were adopted from Ferdinand's (2000) study. This may suggest that the marketing performance indicators used in this study may be an element that helps to differentiate it from the findings of previous studies.

B. The Effect of Customer Orientation on Marketing Performance

The results show that customer orientation has a positive and significant effect on marketing performance, which means that the better the application of customer orientation have a better effect on marketing performance. Customer orientation, as defined by Atuahene-Gima & Ko (2001), symbolises a company's strategy of focusing on the market to gather, disseminate, and act on market intelligence to meet customers' needs. The company's comprehension of consumer objectives

is fundamental in providing exceptional value continually. Perisai Agent is one of BPJS Ketenagakerjaan's approaches to gaining customer insight. The purpose of Perisai Agents is to gather information about the needs and desires of participants because Perisai Agents interact directly with customers. According to Lewrick et al. (2011), an important measure of customer orientation is the collection of data on the requirements of the customer. By collecting this information, Perisai Agents hope to commit themselves to ensuring customer satisfaction by understanding how to meet their needs, addressing any complaints and consistently paying attention to their desires. In addition, BPJS Ketenagakerjaan will benefit from an increased ability to provide the highest quality service to its customers. A customer-centric approach is known to enhance marketing performance. As stated in Sidiq & Astutik's (2017) study, this strategy fosters customer loyalty, stimulates sales growth, and increases customer satisfaction for companies that effectively create customer value. The findings of this investigation confirm Haryanto's (2017) research, which says that the company is able to create customer value. The findings of this investigation confirm Haryanto's (2017) research, which states that the company is able to create customer value. Furthermore, Haryanto et al. (2017) explain that customer orientation has a positive and significant effect on marketing performance. Feng et al. (2012) and Valenzuela et al. (2010) show that customer orientation is very important for companies to better understand customer demand and achieve sales growth.

C. The Effect of Internal Marketing on Interactive Marketing

The findings indicate that internal marketing significantly affects interactive marketing, i.e. the better the internal marketing of employees, the better the effect on interactive marketing. Internal marketing refers to a company's training and motivation initiatives that encourage employees to make the best possible contribution to the marketing of services to consumers (Gronroos, 1990). Interactive marketing, on the other hand, describes the expertise of employees in serving customers. In marketing, it is highly significant to establish two-way communication between customers and employees, where customers share their views, preferences, and choices for products, for the purpose of improving them (Hsieh, 2017). Employees need proper training and motivation to enable such communication. The Perisai Agent's role involves interactive marketing, both face-to-face and online. Their ability to establish effective communication with customers is crucial in carrying out these marketing activities. To further develop this capability, BPJS Ketenagakerjaan provides Perisai Agents with training through an internal marketing programme. This training equips employees with the necessary skills to navigate a rapidly changing environment and encourages innovative thinking. Homburg et.al (2009) argue that good internal marketing enables employees to fully understand customer needs during interactions. service quality and has a positive effect on interactive marketing. Thus, employee-focused interactive marketing can be cultivated through the internal marketing organised by the company. The research findings of this study support Hsieh's (2017) research, which states that there is a positive and significant relationship between internal marketing and interactive marketing.

D. The Effect of Customer Orientation on Interactive Marketing

The findings showed that customer orientation has a significant effect on interactive marketing, which means that the better the implementation of customer orientation have a better effect on interactive marketing. As previously described, Perisai Agent is one of BPJS Ketenagakerjaan's strategies to understand customers or customer orientation. Customer orientation can assist BPJS Ketenagakerjaan Perisai Agents in comprehending customer requirements and preferences, thereby allowing them to create interactive marketing strategies for Perisai Agents that are more effective and relevant. Eric (2017) supports this assertion, indicating that interactive marketing plays a critical role in customer retention in the service industry. Gronroos (2006) argues that a company's market orientation is closely linked to its customer orientation, which enhances its overall performance. To design effective and relevant interactive marketing strategies for Perisai Agent, it is essential to be customer-oriented and understand their needs and wants. Accordingly, each Perisai Agent should prioritize being customer-oriented to achieve a better grasp of customer preferences. By comprehensively understanding their customers, companies can create interactive content that is more appealing and valuable, ultimately resulting in increased customer engagement and satisfaction. This, in turn, can have a significant impact on marketing performance.

E. The Effect of Interactive Marketing on Marketing Performance

Results show significant effects of interactive marketing on marketing performance, suggesting better execution of interactive marketing results in better marketing performance. As interactive marketing becomes more prevalent, customers and companies are interacting and communicating through a variety of channels, increasing their reach. In contemporary times, interactive marketing represents the latest marketing trend due to the dynamic and technologically advanced nature of today's consumers (Wang, 2021). Perisai Agents undertake interactive marketing through creating two-way communication between customers and company marketers, which employs online marketing methods to fulfil consumer needs and desires. Perisai Agents engage in interactive marketing activities by offering direct and interactive customer engagement. They are readily available to help customers with their needs and desires, both in-person at their office and online via call centre or WhatsApp. For illustration, the Perisai agent who is ready to be contacted when a customer has an accident at work, even at night. Perisai agents are available to aid and support the participant's claim process until it reaches completion.

F. The Indirect Effect of Interactive Marketing as an Intervening Variable

Indirect relation testing results show that internal marketing has a significant positive effect on marketing performance with interactive marketing as the mediating variable. However, the first hypothesis of this study found that internal marketing has no significant impact on marketing performance. This confirm that interactive

marketing was able to strengthen the influence of internal marketing relationships on marketing performance. It can be argued that implementing interactive marketing can support internal marketing of Perisai agents, which can improve marketing performance. Interactive marketing can enhance awareness, improve image, and boost sales of products or services. Its direct use in the field encourages Perisai agents to be more motivated, active and productive, and to participate in internal marketing programmes organised by BPJS Ketenagakerjaan NTB. This supports and improves marketing performance.

The test results indicate that customer orientation has a significant effect on marketing performance, with interactive marketing serving as the mediating variable. The test results indicate that customer orientation has a significant effect on marketing performance, with interactive marketing serving as the mediating variable. This supports the second hypothesis of the study. Interactive marketing indirectly impacts customer orientation concerning marketing performance. Interactive marketing can provide support and enhance the impact of customer orientation on marketing performance, thus supporting market-oriented activities. The implementation of interactive marketing by Perisai Agents in the field clearly demonstrates its ability to improve the marketing performance of BPJS Ketenagakerjaan in West Nusa Tenggara. As a customer-focused company, Perisai Agent must be proficient in communicating with customers. Interactive marketing promotes customer acquisition and retention and is considered a method of communication. By creating interactive content, companies can gain a better understanding of their customers, increasing customer loyalty, satisfaction, and ultimately impacting marketing performance. Therefore, interactive marketing can strengthen customer orientation relationships and improve marketing performance. The direct implementation of interactive marketing by Perisai Agent signifies a commitment to market-oriented activities and customer orientation, resulting in a significant enhancement of the marketing performance of BPJS Ketenagakerjaan NTB.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

Based on the research analysis and discussion presented in the previous chapter, the study's conclusions are as follows: (1) Internal marketing has a negative and insignificant effect on marketing performance, which means that the better the implementation impact on internal marketing, no better influence on marketing performance. (2) Customer orientation has a positive and significant effect on marketing performance, meaning that the better the implementation of customer orientation, the better the effect on marketing performance. (3) Internal marketing has a positive and significant effect on interactive marketing, i.e. the better the internal marketing of employees, the better the effect on interactive marketing. (4) The implementation of customer orientation has a positive and significant effect on interactive marketing, i.e. the better the implementation of customer orientation, the better the effect on interactive marketing. (5) Interactive marketing positively and significantly affects interactive marketing, i.e. the better the

implementation of customer orientation, the better the contribution of interactive marketing. (6) Interactive marketing has a significant mediating effect on the correlation between internal marketing and marketing performance, and is a strong indirect factor in this relationship. (7) The correlation between customer orientation and marketing performance is significantly mediated by interactive marketing. As a mediating variable, interactive marketing has a strong indirect effect on the relationship between customer orientation and marketing performance.

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